

Managerial Recommendations for Enhancing Online Shopping Attitude and Intention of Consumers in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Global e-commerce, generally and in Vietnam, is growing strongly. The number of people participating in online shopping is increasing proportionately to the rate of Internet users and product information searches. Consumers mainly use smartphones to access the Internet and participate in online shopping.

Objective: The study aims to examine the key factors influencing online shopping attitudes and intentions in Vietnam and propose managerial recommendations to enhance consumers' online shopping.

Methodology: The authors conducted a descriptive survey based on the quantitative method and primary data collected directly from consumers. We collected data from 700 consumers buying online products from five Vietnamese provinces and cities: Can Tho City, Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai Province, Binh Duong Province, and Ba Ria - Vung Tau Province.

Result: Research results show five factors affecting online shopping attitudes and consumers' intentions based on a five percent significance. Five factors include perceived usefulness (USE), perceived ease of use (EAS), confidence (CON), safety level (SAF), and customer service (SER). The research results also suggest some policy recommendations for state management agencies and online retailers to build consumer trust in online retailers, thereby enhancing the online shopping intention of Vietnamese consumers.

Conclusion: Vietnam is a country with solid development in information technology. The number of customers participating in e-commerce is increasing. Consumers can easily search for products, compare prices, order, pay, and choose a reputable delivery unit. In addition, the current payment methods are very diverse, such as payment cards, e-wallets, or goods received and paid. This helps online shopping activities take place conveniently.

Unique Contribution: The research has developed tailored scales for the variables of trust and perceived usefulness, specifically adapted to the context of online shopping in Vietnam, where this mode of commerce is still in the early stages of its development.

Key Recommendation: The authors suggested that businesses should continue to invest in online marketing because mediated platforms have become useful venues for consumers to purchase different products.

Keywords: Managerial recommendations; online shopping attitude; intention; consumers.

Introduction

Over the past five years, e-commerce platforms have provided various products with flexible and abundant payment methods, allowing consumers to shop online quickly and conveniently. Moreover, in the era of digital technology, the demand for smart devices is increasing, and technology networks are a place to update news and buy, sell, and do business quite effectively to bring sellers and buyers closer together and meet consumers' shopping needs. Instead of going directly to stores to learn, compare, and consult prices, we can do it entirely through digital technology platforms. Minimizing unnecessary contact, ensuring health safety for all

customers. With online ordering, the products in the shopping cart will quickly be delivered to the desired address regardless of day or night. We can proactively prevent contact and know exactly who we have been in contact with and at what time (Nga & Tam, 2024; Saad, 2020; Koay et al., 2022).

Understanding online shopping behaviour, businesses and entities participating in e-commerce activities find solutions and strategies to promote positive factors that positively impact consumers' shopping behaviour and limit negative aspects that harm consumers' shopping behaviour, thereby attracting a large number of consumers and increasing online sales revenue. Below are some solutions for e-commerce trading floors and sellers on the floor to boost online sales revenue:

Nowadays, online shopping is no longer a trend but has become a habit of many people. However, along with convenience comes the situation of traders mixing in selling fake and poor quality goods, causing people to lose confidence when shopping. Online shopping platforms and social media channels have become valuable tools to help brands reach their customers directly. However, counterfeit goods and goods of unknown origin are among consumers' most significant concerns. The larger the number of orders purchased, the more likely they are to buy fake goods of poor quality (Pookulangara et al., 2023).

Currently, the management system of the Department of E-Commerce and Digital Economy records about 900 e-commerce trading floors and about 48,000 direct sales websites or e-commerce applications. Although many e-commerce platforms control the origin of inputs, they still allow counterfeit and poor-quality goods to enter the market. Therefore, control of this form of business needs to be strengthened, and consumers need to pay special attention to checking the legality of the stores. The unfortunate experience of buying fake or poor-quality goods when shopping online has helped Vietnamese consumers positively change their perception and boldly express their consumer rights. Previously, customer feedback on products was minimal, even rare, but platforms and e-commerce floors have recorded increased input and complaints from online customers. It is difficult to quantify the number of consumers scammed by online sellers because returning goods or giving input from victims can only be done through the trading floor. Therefore, consumers have become more careful to protect themselves when participating in this type of shopping. These measures help instil confidence in buyers, making them more comfortable searching for information and purchasing online. Unfortunately, many websites currently overlook these crucial principles. Some businesses have resold or mishandled customer information, leading to cases where bank accounts have been compromised. In such instances, buyers often find themselves without a legal foundation to protect their rights in disputes related to product complaints, leading to a lack of trust in websites with inadequate security measures. This study aims to determine the factors that influence consumer attitudes and intentions toward online shopping and to provide recommendations for managers to foster the growth of online shopping among consumers in Vietnam.

Literature Review

Online Shopping Intention (OSI)

Online shopping allows individuals to independently access information about various policies on the Internet at any moment (Al-Hattami, 2021). Online purchasing is a method businesses use to distribute items without the need for direct interaction between the customer and the company's representative. Online shopping displays goods and services with accompanying imagery using electronic methods, allowing customers to purchase remotely. After choosing the goods or services, the transaction will be executed automatically by online or cash payment. Online buying is a commercial innovation that facilitates electronic and intangible connections to maintain business ties by exchanging information and expertise (Chen &

Demirci, 2019; Lee et al., 2020). The Internet is extensively utilised for many purposes, such as communication, commercial transactions, market structures, education, and jobs. Online purchasing encompasses a range of factors influencing consumer behaviour and the purpose of shopping online. Studies on the determinants of customers' attitudes and intents toward online buying reveal that five key aspects influence online purchasing attitudes: perceived utility, user-friendliness, self-assurance, security level, and quality of customer service (Davis, 1989).

Online Shopping Attitude (OSA)

In the past, customers often engaged in traditional shopping methods, such as purchasing directly from supermarkets, marketplaces, stores, and other locations of sale. This channel is characterised by direct interaction between the supplier and the buyer, where they discuss the conditions and advantages of the product (Chen & Demirci, 2019). However, when relying on an intermediary to communicate the details and lifespan of a product, there is always a potential for asymmetric knowledge, leading to variations in the product. In addition, not all purchasers can physically visit the locations where things are bought and sold (Davis, 1989; Koch et al., 2020). Consequently, adopting Internet shopping will address the limitations of conventional purchasing methods. Product customers' opinions, attitudes, and intentions are crucial factors in influencing online purchasing decisions (Nga & Tam, 2024).

Perceived Usefulness (USE)

Perceived usefulness is another crucial factor that influences online shopping attitudes and intentions. Consumers are more likely to shop online if they believe the platform provides a significant benefit or utility. Perceived usefulness strongly correlates with users' acceptance of new technology (Davis, 1989). In online shopping, when consumers perceive a platform as helpful in providing information, facilitating transactions, and delivering products efficiently, their attitude toward online shopping tends to become more favorable. Digital technology's perceived usefulness has paved the way for numerous benefits, such as easy access to a wealth of information, the ability to quickly and easily find what you're looking for the ability to make requests and receive highly personalized responses, the ability to shop in virtual reality, doorstep delivery, reduced transaction costs, and more (Nga & Tam, 2024).

Perceived Ease of Use (EAS)

Perceived ease of use refers to convenience and is one of the criteria consumers care about when shopping online. Automating transactions through the Website and the Internet helps business activities be carried out at all times. From in-store to online purchases, consumers compare and evaluate items and services more quickly, diversely, and objectively than ever (Alalwan et al., 2018). The customer's purchasing experience and the company's reputation are significantly influenced by the capacity to interact and share comments and evaluations with others. The Internet gives people a better voice to express their ideas, whether they're happy or unhappy, about the products they buy and the services they receive (Davis, 1989).

Confidence (CON)

The confidence in the online vendor reduces the perceived risk associated with online transactions and encourages consumers to engage in online shopping. Trust can be built through positive past experiences, reputation, and the presence of security measures (Alalwan et al., 2018). Trust is crucial in establishing a solid buyer-seller relationship, especially in uncertain situations, vulnerability, and dependence. This becomes even more vital in the online environment, where the perceived risk is heightened due to the lack of direct contact between buyers and sellers and the inability to physically inspect the product before purchase (Nga & Tam, 2024).

Safety Level (SAF)

The perception of security plays a critical role in shaping online shopping attitudes and intentions. Perceived security significantly influences consumers' trust and willingness to shop online. Implementing robust security measures can alleviate these concerns and bolster consumer confidence (Brewer & Sebby, 2021). An online retailer's perceived security is akin to a brand's reputation, encompassing elements like the business's name, logo, design, and distinctive features that identify its products. Perceived security is linked to the company's image and heavily influenced by customer reviews and experiences. Consumers are more likely to trust online retail websites when they perceive the business to have a solid and reputable standing (Nga & Tam, 2024).

Customer Service (CUS)

Customer service is all the activities a business performs to satisfy the needs and wants of customers. These activities can be performed at all stages before, during, and after the customer purchases the business's products/services. Customer care is also understood as a part of a business specialising in customer-related activities (Al-Hattami, 2021; Brewer & Sebby, 2021). Businesses with good customer care services will create a positive experience for new customers and retain old customers longer. Many different factors are needed to sell online effectively and successfully. Customer care is a significant factor that determines the long-term sales effectiveness of a business. Besides, customer care seems simple, but this art requires ingenuity, expertise, and experience. However, it also grasps customer psychology and meets the buyer's psychological needs for effective consulting (Nga & Tam, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

Perceived Usefulness (USE), Online Shopping Attitude (OSA) and Online Shopping Intention (OSI)

Customers can easily find products and freely choose or change products according to their needs, which are linked to attitudes toward technology acceptance, directly impacting user behaviour. A person's adoption of technology is determined by their intention to employ it (Wang et al., 2018). In this context, intent is determined by an individual's disposition towards technology and perception of its utility. An individual's views are shaped by their beliefs on the utilisation of technology (Casalegno et al., 2022). Perceived utility and ease of use are highly influential factors that strongly predict and motivate individuals' desire to use information technology, as demonstrated in several studies on the technology acceptance model (Alalwan et al., 2018; Kang & Namkung, 2019). Therefore, H1 and H2 are proposed in Figure 1.

Perceived Ease of Use (EAS), Online Shopping Attitude (OSA) and Online Shopping Intention (OSI)

Customer perceptions of the potential benefits derived from the ease of control, simplicity of usage, and flexibility in utilising technology. Moreover, when consumers sense a significant level of comfort, their inclination to embrace advanced technology surpasses their inclination to embrace high functionality (Chen & Demirci, 2019). As most studies indicate, convenience and time savings are the primary factors driving customers to make online purchases (Davis, 1989; Natarajan et al., 2018). Research suggests that finding and accessing things and services over the Internet is considerably more efficient and cost-effective. Utilising Internet search engines may efficiently identify satisfactory items and services, whereas traditional purchasing presents challenges such as time consumption and high expenses (Wang et al., 2018). Therefore, H3 & H4 are proposed in Figure 1.

Confidence (CON), Online Shopping Attitude (OSA) and Online Shopping Intention (OSI)

Belief refers to the user's assessment of the likelihood that utilising an application system would enhance job performance, save time efficiently, or improve individual work performance (Wang et al., 2018). These results also pertain to strengthening the effectiveness of online buying and presenting a chance to appeal to global shoppers actively seeking knowledge and uniqueness (Trivedi & Yadav, 2018). Studies indicate that Internet commerce generates allure, ease, and utility, significantly influencing purchase behaviour. Research has identified many critical motivating elements influencing consumers' online search and buying behaviour. These factors include the advantages, confidence, and usefulness of online information and personal experiences (Chen & Aklikokou, 2020). These findings highlight these factors' significant impact on consumers' intentions to search and purchase online. Trust is crucial in developing client connections and constructing a robust Internet sales infrastructure in online purchasing (Kang et al., 2019). Thus, H5 & H6 proposed in Figure 1.

Safety Level (SAF), Online Shopping Attitude (OSA) and Online Shopping Intention (OSI)

Online purchasing alleviates consumer stress by providing a sense of security when selecting a trustworthy supplier, enhancing their overall well-being in both personal and professional aspects of life. Consumers experience increased satisfaction, enhanced happiness, improved social interaction, and security while online buying. Customers occasionally like shopping for leisure rather than fulfilling everyday needs. Many customers engage in shopping activities to enhance their well-being, increase their awareness, and experience pleasure (Trivedi & Yadav, 2018). Simultaneously, customers can establish social ties with both other consumers and providers. Comprehensive descriptions consistently accompany online products. Simultaneously, the Internet shopping system aids clients by storing their personal information and purchase history. Consequently, buyers may significantly save time and expenses by opting for alternative purchasing techniques instead of traditional ones (Brewer & Seby, 2021). Online purchasing enhances convenience and security for consumers by enabling them to select reliable websites. Thus, H7 & H8 proposed in Figure 1.

Customer Service (CUS), Online Shopping Attitude (OSA) and Online Shopping Intention (OSI)

Businesses sometimes utilise additional incentives while selling items or providing customer care services to enhance value and more effectively cater to consumer wants. Online shoppers may access these deals through the Website based on the supplier's social media platforms (Wang et al., 2018). Online customers can purchase anytime and from any location using internet-connected electronic devices. Additionally, they may take advantage of lucrative corporate promotions. Geographical boundaries or time constraints do not limit shopping (Koch et al., 2020; Trivedi & Yadav, 2018). Consumers may effortlessly and promptly contact retailers and receive optimal service assistance, regardless of the time or location. Research indicates that the product may be purchased globally using a touch-enabled electronic device (Casalegno et al., 2022; Nga & Tam, 2024). Therefore, hypotheses H9 and H10 are proposed in Figure 1.

Online shopping attitude affecting online shopping intention.

All of the research, as mentioned above, demonstrates a correlation between attitude and behavioural intention. Greater positivity in attitude correlates with a higher likelihood of customers generating intention. Hence, the study hypothesis posits that attitude directly influences behaviour, and a positive correlation exists between behavioural intention and

attitude. This research approach is generally recognised and commonly used in consumer purchase intention studies. Research findings indicate that attitude significantly influences the intention to buy online (Chen & Aklikokou, 2020). This influence is aligned with convenience and perceived customer advantages (Lee et al., 2020). Studies investigating the correlation between attitudes and beliefs have found that they influence behaviour in several domains, including online buying (Lee et al., 2020; Natarajan et al., 2018). Therefore, hypothesis H11 is proposed in Figure 1.

After examining the studies mentioned above, the authors put up a research model consisting of five components that impact the attitude toward online shopping and positively influence the intention to purchase online in Vietnam. The authors recommend using a structural equation model in the following format.

Source: The authors suggested

Figure 1: The framework for five pivotal aspects that impact online shopping attitude and intention

Figure 1 illustrates five factors that impact the attitude toward and intention to engage in online shopping.

Research Methods

The authors designed the study with two main quantitative stages. These stages are essential for examining, assessing, and analysing the relationship between variables in a theoretical model and detailed contents, followed by ten steps.

Step 1: The authors give the objectives to examine, assess, and analyse the factors in the theoretical model. Based on the findings, propose a research report. Fine-tune and enhance scales derived from previous research to fit the Vietnamese context, considering cultural, linguistic, and developmental differences.

Step 2: The authors applied the quantitative research methodology based on convenience sampling to conduct comprehensive interviews. A total of 11 managers from online shops and 7 experienced online customers participated. Interviews were conducted virtually via direct telephone calls.

Step 3: The authors' number of interviews reached saturation, with no new elements emerging. In-depth interviews demonstrated the applicability of the model's research scales.

Step 4: The authors conducted quantitative research in preliminary and formal phases. The research team used convenience sampling to collect data, with the sample size determined by various parameters (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 5: The sample size is determined by considering various processing techniques such as Cronbach's alpha (with a threshold of greater than 0.7), Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The model fit is assessed using the following criteria: Goodness of Fit Index ($GFI \geq 0.900$), Tucker-Lewis Index ($TLI \geq 0.900$), Comparative Fit Index ($CFI \geq 0.900$), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation ($RMSEA < 0.1$).

Step 6: The sample size is calculated using empirical methods tailored to each analytical approach. The minimum sample size is five times the total number of observed variables ($n = 5 * m$). For a study with 25 observed variables, the minimum sample size for EFA is 125, and for multiple regression analysis, it is 98. The research used 700 survey samples from five Vietnamese provinces and cities: Can Tho City, Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai Province, Binh Duong Province, and Ba Ria-Vung Tau Province. The study population comprises consumers buying online products, which are nearly 10 million persons in Vietnam.

Step 7: The authors applied the questionnaire using a 5-level Likert scale (1 level is strongly disagree, 5 level is strongly agree). 700 survey questionnaires were distributed, and 685 valid responses were collected. Data analysis was performed using SPSS software, employing convenience sampling (Hair et al., 2018).

Step 8: The survey was conducted from July to December 2024 in five Vietnamese provinces and cities: (1) Can Tho had 200 persons: As a significant city in the Mekong Delta, Can Tho represents the online buying behaviours of a region with a growing middle class and increasing internet accessibility. (2) Ho Chi Minh City had 200 persons: Being Vietnam's largest city and economic hub, Ho Chi Minh City is at the forefront of e-commerce adoption, making it a critical area for studying online shopping trends. (3) Dong Nai had 100 persons: Located near Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai offers insights into online buying behaviours in an industrially developed yet suburban area. (4) Binh Duong had 100 persons: As another rapidly industrialising province, Binh Duong provides data on online shopping behaviours in a region experiencing fast economic growth and urbanisation. (5) Ba Ria - Vung Tau had 100 persons: This coastal province, known for its tourism and oil industries, adds a unique perspective to the study, capturing the online buying habits of both locals.

Step 9: The authors applied the comprehensive quantitative survey conducted with 685 consumers. The authors ensured data validity and reliability based on Cronbach's Alpha, which was used to ensure internal consistency and reliability of the scales. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated, aiming for values greater than 0.7. Pilot Testing: Before the formal survey, a pilot test was conducted to refine the questionnaire and ensure the clarity and relevance of the questions, and the official study used confirmatory factor analysis.

Step 10: The authors applied the SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) method to assess the model's appropriateness and research hypotheses. SPSS 20.0 and Amos were used for the initial scale assessment through EFA, CFA analysis, evaluating model fit and research hypotheses. The author tested descriptive statistics to summarise the demographic information and general trends. The authors tested the hypotheses formulated in the theoretical model using SEM to determine the strength and direction of the relationships between variables (Hair et al., 2018). The results were interpreted in the context of the existing literature, highlighting the implications for theory, practice, and future research. Finally, the authors studied to check and standardise scales and questionnaires. The authors' structured approach ensures clarity and comprehensiveness in presenting the research process, objectives, methodology, findings, and analysis. The authors had conclusions and proposed managerial recommendations to enhance online shopping attitudes and consumers' intentions in Vietnam.

Study Results

The research findings show that consumers' attitudes toward online shopping positively influence intention. Specifically, the more favourable a consumer's attitude toward a particular website, the higher their intention to purchase from that Website, with the results below.

Table 1: The results of testing Cronbach's alpha and average value for critical factors

Code Items	Number of items	Code	Cronbach's alpha	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived usefulness (USE)	4	USE1, USE2, USE3, USE4	0.911	2.9967	0.897
Perceived ease of use (EAS)	4	EAS1, EAS2, EAS3, EAS4	0.942	3.0511	0.923
Confidence (CON)	4	CON1, CON2, CON3, CON4	0.857	3.3989	0.779
Safety level (SAF)	4	SAF1, SAF2, SAF3, SAF4	0.935	3.0263	0.889
Customer service (SER)	3	SER1, SER2, SER3	0.907	3.2701	0.902
Online shopping attitude (ATT)	3	ATT1, ATT2, ATT3	0.921	3.2871	0.915
Online shopping intention (INT)	3	INT1, INT2, INT3	0.810	2.3805	0.576

Source: calculations by the authors

Table 1 indicates Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the five significant factors influencing online purchasing attitude and intention in Vietnam exceeds 0.7. In addition, two variables that were shown to be dependent were the attitude toward online purchasing and the desire to purchase online. The data demonstrates high internal consistency across all constructs, as seen by Cronbach's alpha values, all above the widely acknowledged standard of 0.7. This indicates that the items within each component have a high level of reliability when assessing the underlying construct. The average ratings suggest that the participants usually hold favorable attitudes towards online purchasing, perceive it as beneficial and user-friendly, and experience a comparably high level of confidence and security.

Source: The results from SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Figure 2: Evaluating essential elements impacting intent to purchase online and attitude toward online shopping

The model fit indices used to examine the main elements affecting online buying attitudes and intentions are shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows a 0.05 significance test of five main factors impacting Vietnamese Internet purchasing attitudes and intentions. These findings illuminate Vietnamese Internet buying behavior factors.

Table 2: Testing five key factors influencing online shopping attitude and online shopping intention

Relationships	Standardized estimate	Unstandardized estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Result
ATT <--- USE	0.566	0.541	0.036	14.900	***	Accepted H1
ATT <--- EAS	0.091	0.078	0.028	2.748	0.006	Accepted H3
ATT <--- CON	0.178	0.176	0.035	5.069	***	Accepted H5
ATT <--- SAF	0.087	0.083	0.032	2.596	0.009	Accepted H7
ATT <--- SER	0.061	0.090	0.036	2.481	0.013	Accepted H9
INT <--- USE	0.286	0.156	0.027	5.827	***	Accepted H2
INT <--- EAS	0.122	0.060	0.018	3.287	0.001	Accepted H4
INT <--- CON	0.128	0.073	0.022	3.344	***	Accepted H6
INT <--- SAF	0.085	0.046	0.020	2.276	0.023	Accepted H8
INT <--- SER	0.073	0.061	0.023	2.653	0.008	Accepted H10
INT <--- ATT	0.334	0.190	0.029	6.623	***	Accepted H11

*The data was analyzed using SPSS 20.0, Amos, and the significance level is ***, equal to 0.01.*

Table 2 presents the five key factors that significantly impact online shopping attitudes and shopping intentions in Vietnam, which are statistically significant at the 0.05 level. A major contribution of this study is the identification of perceived usefulness (USE) as the most influential factor affecting online shopping attitudes. This factor is quantified by a standardized estimate of 0.541, indicating its substantial impact. Given its prominence, perceived usefulness should be prioritized in policy implementation, as it has important implications for shaping consumer behavior in the online shopping environment.

Table 3: Factors impacting online purchasing attitude and intention: testing average variance extracted

Code	CR	AVE	MSV	Results
ATT	0.922	0.799	0.346	Very good
EAS	0.942	0.804	0.068	Very good
SAF	0.935	0.783	0.016	Very good
USE	0.913	0.724	0.346	Very good
CON	0.853	0.601	0.035	Very good
SER	0.910	0.773	0.016	Very good
INT	0.811	0.588	0.317	Very good

The data was analyzed using SPSS 20.0, Amos.

Table 3 shows that all scales are exceptional and satisfactory; consequently, the emergence of e-commerce and digital technologies has altered consumer purchasing patterns. Digital technology has dramatically enhanced the accessibility of various information sources, enabling consumers to easily search for and find suitable products and services. Additionally, it has empowered consumers to make personalized requests and receive tailored responses. Furthermore, digital technology has revolutionized the shopping experience by allowing

consumers to immerse themselves in virtual reality and enjoy the convenience of home delivery, thereby reducing both time and transaction costs. Internet shopping has revolutionized how we purchase, allowing us to swiftly and objectively compare and evaluate the value of items and services using various information sources.

Table 4: The results of a Bootstrap test using 50.000 samples to determine what variables influence consumers' attitudes and intentions toward online buying

Parameter	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias	CR	Results
ATT <--- USE	0.046	0.001	0.540	-0.002	0.003	-0.67	Good
ATT <--- EAS	0.028	0.001	0.072	-0.006	0.004	-1.50	Good
ATT <--- CON	0.040	0.001	0.170	-0.006	0.004	-1.50	Good
ATT <--- SAF	0.033	0.001	0.076	-0.006	0.004	-1.50	Good
ATT <--- SER	0.044	0.001	0.083	-0.007	0.005	-1.40	Good
INT <--- USE	0.030	0.001	0.156	0.000	0.001	0.00	Good
INT <--- EAS	0.033	0.001	0.060	0.000	0.001	0.00	Good
INT <--- CON	0.022	0.000	0.069	-0.004	0.003	-1.33	Good
INT <--- SAF	0.024	0.001	0.045	-0.001	0.001	-1.00	Good
INT <--- SER	0.029	0.001	0.052	-0.001	0.001	-1.00	Good
INT <--- ATT	0.031	0.001	0.192	0.001	0.001	1.00	Good

The authors used SPSS 20.0, Amos, as a data source.

Table 4 presents the Bootstrap method, employing a sample size of 50.000 treated as the population, which was utilized to ensure robust and reliable estimates. The average forecasts from these samples closely align with the population estimates, supporting the study's findings. The results show that the variables in the model are appropriate, all observed variables are retained in the scale, and are an essential basis for proposing management implications to improve user experience by designing user interfaces. Simple and easy-to-use website interface, suitable for all access devices, personalizing the online shopping experience and recommending appropriate products based on shopping history, search behavior, and user preferences.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in Table 2 provide numerous crucial insights into the links between perceived characteristics and their impact on online purchasing attitude and intention. These findings explain the factors influencing customers' attitudes and behaviors about internet purchasing. The findings illustrate the hierarchical importance of elements, with usefulness, confidence, and attitude playing the most critical roles, while ease of use, safety, and customer service make more subtle but still considerable contributions. Moreover, the association between online shopping attitude and intention is one of the model's most robust based on the standardized estimate of 0.334. This research suggests that customers' sentiments toward online buying strongly predict their shopping propensity. This lends credence to the widely held belief that attitude is a significant predictor of behavior in consumer research. Positive experiences, opinions, and attitudes about online shopping platforms directly impact future purchasing decisions. As a result, online businesses should prioritize improving consumers' views toward online buying, as this considerably impacts purchase behavior (Brewer & Sebby, 2021; Chen & Aklikokou, 2020; Nga & Tam, 2024). Furthermore, the findings in Table 2 highlight the role of perceived utility, confidence, and a positive attitude in motivating online shopping behavior. E-commerce companies should improve their platforms' usefulness and value while instilling consumer trust through transparent and safe processes. Although safety, customer service, and

convenience of use are vital, they are secondary compared to the core factors. To enhance consumer engagement and online sales, firms should create a favorable overall shopping experience, given the significant relationship between attitude and intention.

The online buying mindset mediates customer opinion of online purchasing. Positive attitudes regarding online buying are generally influenced by the five factors above. Online buying intentions are strongly correlated with this mindset. Consumers' future plans to purchase online are sometimes called online shopping intentions. The criteria mentioned above determine a consumer's chance of online shopping. After synchronous conversations, SEM testing identified five significant characteristics influencing online shopping attitude and intention, with sig. 0.05. The report suggests some policies for online shopping platform administrators to boost sales channels and attract more people to online buying. Online purchase attitude is favourably influenced by perceived utility, with a high standardised estimate of 0.566 and a significant p-value of $p < 0.001$. Finally, perceived utility most influences online purchase intention. The highest normalised estimate of all online purchasing intention characteristics is online buying attitude. The findings demonstrate that increasing online platforms' perceived usability and developing a positive attitude about online commerce might increase online purchase intentions (Koch et al., 2020; Trivedi & Yadav, 2018; Chen & Aklikokou, 2020).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study found numerous key elements affecting Vietnamese online purchasing attitudes and intentions. Perceived utility and online shopping attitudes influence consumers' buying intentions the most. Perceived usefulness boosts online shopping attitudes and intentions. Safety, confidence, and customer service also matter, but less. The investigation shows that a favorable online buying attitude strongly influences shopping intentions. This good attitude is influenced by platform confidence, simplicity of use, perceived safety, and customer service. These characteristics have a moderate effect on online shopping intention compared to attitude. Based on the findings, the authors made proposals to simultaneously increase online purchasing attitudes and intentions in Vietnam:

E-commerce platforms should provide features that enhance the shopping experience, such as personalized recommendations, convenient payment options, and efficient delivery services. Highlighting the practical benefits and time savings associated with online shopping can strengthen consumers' perceptions of usefulness. Improve perceived ease of use based on the design of user-friendly interfaces that are easy to navigate, especially for less tech-savvy users. Simplifying the checkout process, providing clear instructions, and offering multilingual support can reduce perceived barriers to use and improve overall ease of use. A marketing communication strategy for the product business, focusing on enhancing internet marketing. This includes planning promotional programs and offering discounts on home items to encourage customers to purchase. Providing discount vouchers to existing customers to attract new consumers; Utilizing email marketing or electronic newsletters to persuade clients to make recurring purchases.

Strengthening customer service based on exceptional customer service by quickly resolving issues, flexible return policies, and proactive communication can enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. To improve the customer service process, it is essential to provide comprehensive product information and promptly equip the customer care staff with the necessary knowledge to address consumer inquiries upon receiving their calls. Concerning packing, it is essential to modify the packaging to allow clients to effortlessly open and inspect the merchandise upon delivery. The goods can be returned free of charge if they fail to meet expectations. Regarding shipping time, it is vital to expedite the delivery of home items owing to their immediate requirement. Implementing this strategy will enhance the Website's ability to create a favorable impression on customers and reduce the occurrence of customer

indecision resulting in non-receipt of products.

Limitations and future research: The study focuses on Vietnam and sheds light on Internet buying attitudes and intentions in this particular setting. However, the findings may not apply to other countries based on the cultural, economic, and technical differences, which may be more important in various markets. The study's sample size and demographic diversity may also limit its strength. Increased sample size and diversity may give more comprehensive and inclusive observations of customer groups' online shopping patterns. Future studies should include different nations or areas to compare how cultural, economic, and technical variations affect online buying attitudes and intentions. This would help apply the findings to other markets. Finally, researchers might examine social influence, brand reputation, website aesthetics, and digital marketing's impact on online purchases.

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